

PARENT'S STRESS MANAGEMENT AND WELL-BEING IN THE MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING: INPUT TO AN ENHANCED SCHOOL MANAGEMENT PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

Covid-19 pandemic has a profound effect on education system. As it puts face-to-face learning into halt, parents find themselves at the frontlines of education. They are subjected to vast challenges and increasing complexities of teaching and learning process among their children. This study aimed to determine the stress management and well-being of parents to help address stress adopting modular distance learning. This study is a descriptive -correlational kind of research in which it uses a survey questionnaire for easier distribution and collection of data. There were 150 parents-respondents of Calitcalit Elementary School, East District of San Juan, Division of Batangas, conducted last April 2021. Based on the result the parents' management of stress is always observable in terms of time management, self-leadership and emotion regulation. Social support is appeared to be sometimes observable in the study. Despite the presence of stress caused by rigorous workloads at home and outside of work, parents are able to manage their responsibilities, accomplish work with good performance and involve themselves effectively in home-schooling of their children. They ensure to provide rich, conducive learning environment to their children, support them in their studies, making them their number one priority. It was also found that parents' total well-being is sometimes affected by the stress brought by the new normal education implementing modular distance learning. The researcher recommends that parents should practice a healthy lifestyle free from stress caused by numerous responsibilities. Maintaining a balance state in family-related and work-related obligations is vital to ensure an optimum well-being. Moreover, igniting social support among teachers, parents, and school administrators is significant to fill in the gap between parents and teachers most especially in these trying times of Covid-19 where learning takes place at home. Teachers must maintain their harmonious relationship with parents to help them in delivering education to their children.

Keywords: Stress Management, Parents Well-being, Modular Distance Learning